

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PROJECT-TELLING AS A NEW AND EFFECTIVE METHOD OF EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS' RECOGNITION

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Abstract

This work is devoted to a new methodology in the management and marketing of educational organizations named Project-telling. The essence and content of the unique methodology Project-telling are considered in the present article. Project-telling has shown its effectiveness in positioning universities and colleges and has significant potential for application in organizations of the non-profit sector - healthcare and medicine, charity and volunteering, sports and culture.

Keywords: Project-telling, project, marketing of educational organizations, positioning of universities, positioning of colleges, expertise of educational organizations, recognition of educational organizations, market for educational services

Education is one of the most conservative areas, where the formation, preservation and development of traditions, methodologies, approaches, scientific and pedagogical schools provide its main functions as the transfer of professional knowledge to next generations, education and comprehensive development of the individual. All over the world, education strives for the consistent development of traditions, which preserved and accumulated over centuries, carefully integrate and responding to the technological development of society and the economy. Positioning projects in education are a relatively new concept with many meanings and interpretations.

I had to observe and work with projects during a period of shaped discussions about the expedient of changes in education, and during a period of rejection in the education system of innovative solutions, approaches and projects, and during a period of complex and painstaking implementation, and during the period of the so-called fashion for innovative projects in education, when joining all sorts of projects became the norm in educational organizations, which began to lead to large-scale burndown and turnover of talented, creative and innovatively thinking staff among employees.

The peculiarity of the implementation of such projects changing public consciousness was the essence contradiction, which continues to remain urgently - a conservative personnel environment, traditionalism, rootedness, and stability of the system, on the one hand. And yet, on the other hand, there is an emerging and rapidly developing market for educational services and competition between educational institutions.

There was a need to promote, search for unique competitive advantages, and expertise of the organization in the educational services market, including in

competition for a larger amount of funding. This is how interest in gradual independent development began to appear, the search for franchise projects, their implementation, testing and approbation.

However, these processes were carried out in an environment unprepared for the implementation of projects. There is still a shortage of motivation and strategic, systematic and competent operational management in projects implemented by educational organizations.

The purpose of this article is to describe the Project-telling methodology as an effective method of positioning an educational organization that solves the problems of transformation, renewal, development in the context of a traditional and conservative organization culture.

Objectives of this article are to demonstrate the working decisions of some key questions at the universities and colleges as:

1. What is the role of the project in education?
2. How to integrate the project as harmoniously as possible into the work of an educational organization with maximum long-term effect?
3. How to motivate those who are not ready for product thinking and missionary thinking to become the most important ambassadors for the organization's promotion?

Scientific validity and practical testing of the Project-telling approach

The Project-telling approach was a continuation of the scientific research "University brands in the Educational Services Market" 2004-2009¹. This approach was tested and showed its effectiveness in the framework of the following projects at educational organization in Russia: the career guidance business game "Trajectory"², the university movement of the WorldSkills

¹ Anisimova, I.A. Brands of universities through the eyes of employers: the degree of trust in the quality of training of specialists / I.A. Anisimova // Vestnik of Nizhny Novgorod University. N.I. Lobachevsky: Social Sciences Series No. 1 (9). - N. Novgorod: Publishing house of Nizhny Novgorod

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² Anisimova, I.A. Methodological recommendations for organizing a career guidance business game "Trajectory":

championships of professional excellence, the program for including advanced professional competencies in the educational programs of universities “Future Skills University”³, the career guidance magazine “Ladder”, the soft-skills development program “Management of Career”, career development school “Marketing of Professional Development”⁴ and etc.

By carefully analyzing the results of projects implemented using the Project-telling methodology, the hypothesis was repeatedly confirmed that this technique, in addition to its importance for management and effective project management, has a significant marketing effect⁵.

The key concept of positioning activities is the project. Developed on the basis of practical experience, this term can be defined as:

A project is an activity organized within a certain time frame and using predetermined resources to solve a problem (divergence between expectations and reality) or achieve a high-level goal to obtain a unique one-time and deferred result. The project is a tool for targeted and controlled changes.

The peculiarity and dominant of Project-telling is in combining marketing and management approaches to achieve the goal of in-depth and sustainable positioning, which is especially valuable in today’s rapidly changing world. The key project question in the Project-telling logic is: what does the problem-solving activity (i.e., the project) tell the organization’s target audience?

The meaning of the Project-telling method in the marketing of educational organizations

Marketing of educational services as a practice-oriented approach began to take shape in the 70s of the 20th centuries as part of “Social Marketing”, which is understood as defined by F. Kotler⁶, “planning, execution and control of programs aimed at achieving the adoption of any social idea, project or task of the target population.” Social marketing is present in the activities of non-profit organizations (educational, public, cultural, sports, medical organizations), the goal of which is to achieve a specific social effect.

The authors of the book “Marketing of Nonprofit Organizations” M. Kinnell and D. McDougall note that organizations are slow to accept the concept of marketing and are slow to come to the need for full application of its principles and tools. However, every year more and more non-profit organizations come and will come

to understand that both strategic planning and professional and comprehensive implementation of marketing activities are necessary.

The development of a market for educational services necessitates the development of promotion strategies for educational organizations, which become the most important condition for their economical survival in a competitive environment. The educational market today offers a wide range of services provided not only by public or state but also by private educational institutions. Each organization faces the issue of promoting its services, on the one hand, to retain adherents and maintain the level of economic functioning, and on the other hand, to expand the number and improve the quality of its applicants and solve the problems of economic development.

The value of education in society, transformed into a motive for receiving it, is quite high, but often comes into conflict with the labor market’s ability to provide qualified work to all those receiving higher education. In addition, employers, who are one of the target groups of universities, have their own ideas about universities, the quality of their training of specialists and are, in fact, the control link in the functioning of the “applicant-educational organization-employer” chain, in which the organization sells an educational service of a certain quality for subsequent (as the applicant believes) employment.

Modern problems of education are studied within the framework of the sociology of education, economic sociology, sociology of knowledge, and sociology of management. To consider consumer behavior in the modern market of educational services, we apply a number of theoretical aspects of social knowledge: marketing of education; human capital theory; the concept of the sociology of knowledge, representing knowledge as a commodity; concepts of value-motivational strategies for student choice; concepts of career preferences; university management concepts.

Marketing strategy is the main tool of classical marketing, which helps to tell target groups and the general public about the organization, position and promote the organization’s products and services. Economic transformation, which requires development in the product line, also entails social changes - public expectations change, types of target groups change, the effectiveness of information channels changes, aesthetic tastes, and reactions to a designer product (service packaging) change. An effective marketing strategy is based on the target audience, its characteristics and needs.

Methodological manual. – Nizhny Novgorod: Nizhny Novgorod State University named after. N.I. Lobachevsky, 2016. – 26 p.

³ Anisimova, I.A. Strategy and modern forms of development of professional competencies in an engineering university // Seventh international scientific and practical conference: Philosophy and culture of the information society: abstracts: at 2 o'clock. Part 2. – St. Petersburg: GUAP, 2019. – P.123-125. – ISBN 978-5-8088-1413-40 (Part 2)

⁴ Voronin, G.L., Anisimova, I.A. Sociological research program of the Career Center of Lobachevsky University in the design and implementation of activities for vocational guidance, employment and professional career implementation

of students and graduates // Helping professions: scientific justification and innovative technologies / Under the general editorship of prof. Z.H. Saralieva. – N.Novgorod: Publishing house NISOC, 2016. – P. 315-318. - ISBN 978-5-93116-183-9.

⁵ Anisimova I.A. Project-telling: positioning by projects / Anisimova I.A. - Moscow: Litres, 2024. - 177 p. - ISBN - 978-5-532-90770-6.

⁶ Kotler, F. Strategic marketing of non-profit organizations / F. Kotler, A.R. Andreasen. – M.: Phoenix, 2007. – 854 p. – ISBN 978-5-222-11766-8

The effectiveness of marketing strategy management is expressed in an established system of “selling” a product or service (when all places are filled) and profit growth.

In the last decade, the formation and increase in the scale of the information and public field of activity of educational organizations has most clearly manifested itself, in which colleges, universities, public aggregator organizations, organizations of additional professional education manifest themselves in the form of projects.

With the increasing role of information on the Internet, as well as the degree of involvement of target groups in Internet communities, projects and positioning in the context of the discourse, meanings and agendas of the current information and public field come to the fore in the promotion of educational organizations (educational organizations, in fact, talk about their uniqueness and features through projects). Thus, Project-telling is becoming the leading method of positioning educational organizations.

Management of storytelling projects in education

Traditionally, when implementing projects, organizations focus on management and, most often, on operational management. It should be noted that micromanagement is certainly important, however, in modern digital conditions, when most routine operations can and should be digitized, the success factor of the project is primarily strategic management decisions for positioning the expertise of an educational organization using the Project-telling method.

In order to assess the fundamental nature and importance of strategic management decisions in education management, let us turn to the scientific study of this issue.

The deep theoretical core of management in education are the theories of post-industrial society, knowledge economy, and human capital.

The theory of post-industrial society is outlined in the works of D. Bell, J. Gilbert, I. Massoud, K. Nodstrom, T. Rozak, O. Toffler, F. Webster, J. Fourastier, clarified as the methodological basis of the information economy in the studies of M. Porat, J. Stigler, K. Arrow. The works of D. Amidon, P. Drucker, F. Machlup, F. Hayek, J. Schumpeter are devoted to the economics of knowledge. The study of the conditions for the formation of a knowledge economy in Russia is reflected in the works of M.G. Delyagin, D.S. Lvova, V.L. Makarova, N.V. Manokhina, T.N. Nikolaeva, T.E. Stepanova, V.V. Chekmareva. You can read more about new management methods used in the knowledge economy in the books of R. Buckman, L. Brown, B. Gates, B. Schmidt and others.

An evolutionary approach to the analysis of the economic dynamics of knowledge and the learning process in the context of accelerating economic development is presented in the works of P. David, J. Metcalfe, J. Mokyr, R. Nelson, N. Rosenberg, S. Winter and others.

In the aspect of managing a higher education institution in market conditions, as well as increasing the role of universities in a knowledge-based economy, the

works of D. Gaston, P. Kaisenshao, A.O. are interesting. Oleynik, V.M. Polterovich, F. Santos, M.M. Skoreva, V.L. Tambovtseva, R. Florida, M. Heitora, A.E. Shastitko, V.D. Shchetinin, R.G. Strongin, A.O. Grudzinsky (project-oriented university), A.Yu. Slepukhin (higher education in the context of globalization), Ya.I. Kuzminov, G.G. Kantorovich, V.V. Pisyakov (innovations in the activities of the university)⁷.

What is different between project management in education and management in education?

✓ Goal and result are the key to the project. The project is not intended to replace, compete with, or create new functions and processes at the college or university - this is the prerogative of the organization's management. However, it can create new products and services in the organization.

✓ The project has a clear deadline with an assessment of the result. Management of an educational organization is the constant management of processes and the performance of functions - career guidance, educational, educational, educational, social, research, etc.

✓ The project team is a miniature of the organization. The project team is formed for the project with clear assignment of roles and functions for the success of the project. This is always the search and testing of new and non-standard working solutions and their normative consolidation for the effectiveness of the project in education. This requires a lot of time, flexibility and creativity.

✓ The place of the project in the organization is visual, measurable changes. The purpose of the organization's management is operation and planned development.

Classical organizational management focuses on process management. The application of classical management approaches ensures stability and sustainable functioning of any organization and allows achieving average results at the level of self-sufficiency and self-reproduction.

The development of classical approaches and an increase in the level of management, and, as a consequence, the level and scale of the organization, an increase in productivity and profit, and the formation of uniqueness is carried out today due to six new key components:

- digitalization of business process management;
- financial management and asset management;
- modeling and transformation of a product or service to meet the challenges of a changing market;
- export of product/service and international relations.
- flexibility in marketing strategy due to constant communication with target audiences;
- implementation of innovations.

Digitalization of business process management is a large-scale direction in management based on automation, digitalization and optimization of document flow, making management and production decisions, organizing the efficient use of working time, increasing the availability of the organization's main services for

⁷ Grudzinsky, A.O. Project-oriented university. Professional entrepreneurial organization of the university. Project-oriented university [ed. R.G. Strongin] / A.O. Grudzinsky. –

N.Novgorod: Publishing House of Nizhny Novgorod State University, 2004. – 370 p.

the target audience through the implementation and improvement of CRM systems, Agile -systems, LMS systems.

The result of digitalization of business process management is an increase in labor productivity, sales growth through the creation of Internet formats for purchasing and receiving a product or service, and the emergence and development of Internet areas in services.

Financial management and asset management implies competent strategic and operational planning for the management of the organization's finances and property complex. A trending direction today, successfully introduced in the 50s. XX century in the USA, and then became part of European universities and colleges, is the effective management of buildings and premises of an educational organization. Increasing property profitability without risking the organization's brand.

Modeling and transformation of a product or service to meet the challenges of a changing market. The waves of economic change are becoming denser, and the frequency of their occurrence has been increasing over the past 100 years. Rapidly changing economic conditions require equally rapid changes in the products and services of educational organizations for staffing, scientific and technological, socio-political and cultural support of changes.

The introduction of innovation is the highest level in the management of organizations, at which the development and implementation of new products/services, services, and technologies occurs. Experience shows that innovation is most effectively implemented in the form of a project according to the rules and principles of project management. The ultimate goal of introducing innovation is to offer new products/services, services, developments, and technologies that are relevant and in demand for the changing market; opening new market niches and forming a new type of target audience.

The development and implementation of innovative projects is preceded by a period of research to study:

- ✓ macro-, meso- and microeconomic processes and problems in a certain segment,
- ✓ target audiences, their expectations and preferences,
- ✓ economic analysis of opportunities and risks, taking into account the existing or potential competence of the organization in the development and implementation of innovation.

Twenty years of experience in the education system (2004 – 2023) during the period of radical economic transformations, development and institutionalization of international collaboration, has shown that, basically, educational organizations successfully cope with the first two components of development, digitalization of business process management and financial management and asset management.

In terms of modeling and transformation of a product or service to meet the challenges of a changing market, export of a product/service to international markets, flexibility of a marketing strategy taking into account the target audience and the introduction of innovations, the picture among educational organizations of both secondary vocational education and

higher education is quite heterogeneous. There are isolated brilliant examples, and there are many organizations where innovative projects are not considered.

Own projects and projects with participation, innovative solutions, new events occupy a significant part of the educational organization's information materials on the official website, on social networks, and in presentation events. However, the vast majority of them do not work for marketing and financial tasks.

A common practice of organizations is the implementation of the external side of marketing and innovation, formalism. It seems that there is a marketing strategy on paper, and something in the area of advertising is carried out mainly through product design, and the project contains the word "innovation" or its synonym in the title, but no fundamental changes occur.

What projects of an educational organization are we talking about in the current and rapidly developing conditions of the information and public field? About projects that demonstrate the quality or expertise of educational organizations in the main areas of core activity: personnel training, applied research and fundamental science, youth policy, culture and socio-political activities, the demand for graduates in the labor market, vocational and professional guidance, career.

Examples of such projects can be subject Olympiads, conferences, forums, symposiums, network universities, network colleges, network, joint or new educational programs, championships of professional excellence, volunteer movement, professional tests, job fairs, career days, business games, scientific research projects, further educational programs, training schools, bootcamps, etc.

Today in business practice the phrase "Innovation project" is quite common, which applies to the groups of projects listed above. The concept is quite vague and, in most cases, can be defined as a "New Project". In order not to introduce the reader to the subtleties of terminology, in this work we will talk about projects that have the potential to change the situation (abbreviated as change projects). It is precisely changes in the public perception of the target audience that the project, implemented using the Project-telling method, is aimed at.

The success of change projects in education lies in a deep understanding of the essence and place of the project in the organization. Change projects are an individual signature and a unique feature of an educational organization. How to form them? On the one hand, there are conditions set by nature for the formation of handwriting and character traits, and on the other hand, much depends on how this feature is set and presented. This is exactly what the Project-telling method is about.

Purpose, core and principles of the Project-telling method

The goal of the Project-telling approach is the controlled positioning of the unique expertise of an educational organization in the field of training, research and science, youth policy, culture and socio-political activities, the demand for graduates in the labor market, professional guidance and careers.

The key to the Project-telling method is expertise, not the practice of uninterrupted functioning of certain aspects or processes that has developed over the years, only - expertise. Expertise is understood as a direction

that has socio-economic recognition (market value, scientific weight, 100% demand for graduates in the specialized professional labor market, etc.) that corresponds to the strategy and mission of the educational organization.

The core of the Project-telling method is represented by four mandatory layers:

1. A product in demand - solving a problem for the target audience or achieving high-order goals (dreams, ideals) – What does Project-telling tell?
2. Competence of product manufacturers (unique expertise) – Why does Project-telling tell?
3. Design, packaging, contextual marketing – How does Project-telling tell?
4. Location, employees and product ecosystem – Where and Who does Project-telling tell?

Basic principles of the Project-telling method:

- clear knowledge of traditions and a deep understanding of the essence of each service and product in a particular educational organization.
- selection of a network project or development of your own project is implemented as a new packaging of an existing educational service and traditions.
- mandatory compliance with project management elements.
- goal setting: the place of the project in the positioning of the brand of the educational organization.
- the project is implemented according to the classical canons of public relations (PR) as a management function to establish mutually beneficial cooperation between the organization and the target audience, using business rules and approaches in organizing the press service and information coverage.
- the target audience determines the format, design, techniques, volume of content,
- not only the result and fact of the implemented project is important, but also no less important is the socio-economic effect.

Functions and meaning of Project-telling

Project-telling is a multifunctional method that contributes to the comprehensive development of the organization. Let's take a closer look at the functions of the method.

Functions of the Project-telling method:

1. Provides in-depth and sustainable positioning of the educational organization in the information field, because based on the uniqueness and expertise of the educational organization,
2. Contributes to the development and improvement of the level of competencies of the administrative and management team in the field of project management, organization management, etc.,
3. Works for create and strengthen internal corporate motivational communications, an organizational culture around which the team rallies and proudly carries this mission in its professional activities and business environment,
4. Forms long-term partnerships with leading stakeholders, media, representatives of industry, public

organizations, authorities to expand business opportunities and projects in the future,

5. Develops qualitative and quantitative characteristics of clients, increases the volume of investment in an educational organization due to the fact that the introduction of the Project-telling methodology carries out a controlled change in the consciousness of the target group on the theme of the project.

So, Project-telling is a method of developing and implementing projects that change the socio-economic situation within and around the organization, built on positioning the organization's expertise with the help of a popular product (solves problems of the target audience or achieves high-order goals), packaging that is interesting to the target audience (design, contextual marketing) and established business infrastructure (trained employees and partner ecosystem).

Project-telling ensures deep and sustainable positioning of the organization, increases internal corporate involvement and pride, develops administrative and managerial competencies, forms long-term partnerships, and also leads to qualitative and quantitative changes in potential clients and partners.

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